

**EFFECTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE TO TEACHING AND LEARNING
IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS OF ZONE 2,
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Effects of Climate Change to Teaching and Learning in Public Secondary Schools of Zone 2, Division of Zambales

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Abstract

The rapid effects of climate change threaten teaching and learning, necessitating analysis and mitigation. Awareness and prevention are key strategies for meaningful and sustainable development in our changing climate. This study investigated the effects of climate change on teaching and learning in Zone 2, Schools Division of Zambales. A survey questionnaire was used to gather data from teacher-respondents, observing anonymity and informed consent. Findings indicated that teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the effects of climate change on teaching and learning, with a very high positive correlation between the two aspects. There was also a very low negative correlation between the effects of climate change on teaching and student academic performance. An action plan was proposed to address the effects of climate change on teaching and learning, including initiatives such as climate change awareness campaigns, classroom management strategies, curriculum adjustments, and infrastructure improvements in Zone 2, Schools Division of Zambales. These measures aim to equip schools and educators to handle the effects of climate change effectively and sustainably. Further studies in describing perceptions on the effects of climate change in teaching and learning may be conducted involving other variables and other locations to validate further results obtained from this study.

Keywords: *climate change, awareness campaigns, effects of climate change, mitigation, survey questionnaire*

Introduction

The Global Climate Risk Index 2020 list the Philippines as the topmost affected country by climate change, using 2018's data. Since the Philippines is an archipelago lies in the western Pacific Ocean, it is surrounded by naturally warm waters that will likely get even warmer as the average sea surface temperatures continue to rise, (Haiyan, 2016). Jabines and Inventor (2007), likewise, the country is considered as one of the climate hotspots due to its geographical location and low level of economic development, further aggravate by its people's poor access to resources.

Climate change is characterized based by comprehensive long-haul temperature and precipitation trends as well as other components such as precipitation trends, as well as components' such as pressure and humidity level in the surrounding environment. Besides, the irregular weather patterns, retreating of global ice sheets, and the corresponding elevated sea level rise are among the most renowned international and domestic effects of climate change (Abbass, Qasim, Song, Murshed, Mahmood & Younis (2022). Drastic changes in temperature and rainfall levels are predicted. Droughts will be more intense and frequent, as well as typhoons and consequently flooding and landslides. The country has experienced the world's strongest storm to make landfall in the Philippine history, the typhoon Yolanda or Haiyan. The devastation from that typhoon propelled the country to the top of the list of the most vulnerable countries to climate change based on the annual Global Climate Risk Index of Germanwatch (Ranada, 2015).

There is no region on the planet where the ability to educate children is insulated from the effects of climate change. Increases in rainfall, flooding, wildfires, droughts, disease, cyclonic storms, food scarcity, sea level rise, and snowstorms have been attributed to human-induced climate change. Such events are expected to increase in frequency and intensity through at least the near term, 2021–2040. (Pörtner, Roberts, Tignor, Poloczanska, Mintenbeck, Alegría, Craig, Langsdorf, Löschke, Möller, Okem & Rama, 2022) .

Most teachers report that students are struggling to concentrate in class and are not showing up to school due to "intolerable" heat in classrooms, a survey conducted by the country's largest organization of teachers showed. According to results of a survey of 11,706 public school teachers from March 24 to 27, most lessons are also held in congested classrooms, posing severe difficulties for students with medical conditions as summer rolls in (Chi, 2023).

In light of these realities, a mandate of schools will be to provide the skills and abilities needed to survive and thrive in a depleted ecosystem. For all but a scarce collection of indigenous and alternative cultural groups, new ways of thinking and living which are not presently realized must be invented and learned, or perhaps relearned, to achieve global sustainability (Newsome, Newsome, & Miller, 2023).

Understanding the intricate interplay on the impact of climate change to teaching and learning in public secondary schools is of paramount importance. The insights derive from this research can guide educational policymakers, school administrators, and relevant stakeholders in developing strategies and support systems to bolster teacher resilience and optimize student outcomes.

This study is endeavored to uncover the effects of climate change to teaching and learning and the students' scholastic achievements within the context of public secondary education in Masinloc, Division of Zambales.

Furthermore, the study in the Schools Division of Zambales, added a distinct local flavor to these challenges. The geography, socioeconomic factors, and educational infrastructure in this area contribute to unique circumstances that warrant special attention.

The urgency of this study is underscored by the critical need to comprehend the intricate relationship between climate change and its impact on teaching and learning. The educational landscape is intricately connected to environmental conditions, and disruptions caused by climate change can significantly affect the overall learning experience. The aim of the study is to contribute valuable insights that inform the development of adaptive educational strategies, fostering resilience and sustainability in public secondary schools in Zone 2, Division of Zambales.

Research Questions

The study was conducted to describe the teachers' perception on the effects of climate change in teaching and learning in Zone 2, Schools Division of Zambales.

1. How do the teacher-respondents perceive the effects of climate change in teaching as to:
 - 1.1. classroom management;
 - 1.2. classroom activities;
 - 1.3. students' concentration;
 - 1.4. students' attendance;
 - 1.5. students' participation in class discussion;
 - 1.6. students' health; and
 - 1.7. physical infrastructure?
2. How do the teacher-respondents perceive the impact of climate change in student's learning as to:
 - 2.1. classroom management;
 - 2.2. classroom activities;
 - 2.3. students' concentration;
 - 2.4. students' attendance;
 - 2.5. students' participation in class discussion;
 - 2.6. students' health; and
 - 2.7. physical infrastructure
3. What is the level of academic performance of the students?
4. Is there significant difference on the perception of teachers on the impact of climate change to students learning?
5. Is there significant difference on the perception of teachers on the impact of climate change on their teaching?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the impact of climate change to teaching and learning?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the impact of climate to teaching and academic performance?
8. What action plan may be proposed based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

This section presents various steps to actualize the objective. It includes the discussion of the research design, respondents and research locale, instrumentation with discussion of validation of the instrument, data collection and analysis of the data.

Research Design

This research employed a descriptive research method with the survey questionnaire as the main research instrument. A descriptive survey method design was used to collect data from teacher-respondents; which is suitable to all individuals by exploring them as they are in their settings (Siedlecki, 2020). Descriptive method was the most useful method for this study, considering that the researchers shall focus on the present situation (what is) regarding the topic of impact of climate change within the context of teaching and learning.

Descriptive research according to Sirisilla (2023) provides a detailed and accurate picture of the characteristics and behaviors of a particular population or subject. By observing and collecting data on a given topic, descriptive research helps researchers gain a deeper understanding of a specific issue and provides valuable insights that can inform future studies. Descriptive research as described by Salaria (2012 as cited in Catacutan & de Guzman, 2017) involves and employs the process of inquiry, interpretation of condition that exist and attempts to develop knowledge.

The research described the result of the impact of climate change to teaching and learning in public Secondary Schools in Zone 2, Schools Division of Zambales. The perceptions and insights were solicited from the teacher-participants. The result correlated to the students' performance.

Participants

The respondents of the research were the teachers of Zone 2, DepEd Division of Zambales. Table 1 below shows the frequency distribution of the respondents by school.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Teacher – Respondents from Secondary and Integrated Schools of Zone 2, Division of Zambales*

Public Secondary Schools	Teachers (f)	Percentage
Rofulo Landa National High School	5	4.35%
Locloc National High School	5	4.35%
Zambales National High School	10	8.7%
JESMAG National High School	7	6.09%
Amungan National High School	5	4.35%
Bancal Integrated School	9	7.83%
Bangan-Capayawan Integrated School	5	4.35%
Beneg National High School	12	10.40%
Botolan National High School	15	13.04%
Botolan North Integrated School	7	6.09%
Carael Integrated School	5	4.35%
New Taugtog National High School	10	8.7%
Panan National High School	5	4.35%
San Isidro Integrated School	5	4.35%
Mambog Integrated School	5	4.35%
Santiago Integrated School	5	4.35%
Total	115	100%

As shown in Table 1, a total population of one hundred fifteen (115) secondary teachers were identified as respondents of the study. They are all employed in the sixteen (16) schools of Zone 2, Division of Zambales. The teacher were randomly chosen as respondents.

Figure 2 below shows the map of the locations of the school respondents.

Figure 1. *Map of Zambales showing the Location of the High Schools in the 3 Districts of Zone 2, Division of Zambales*

The study was conducted at Public High Schools and Integrated Schools of the three (3) Districts (Botolan District, Iba District and Palauig District) of Zone 2, DepEd Division of Zambales. Iba District includes Zambales National High School, Iba; Amungan National High School, Brgy. Amungan, Iba; and Jesus F. Magsaysay High School, Brgy. Bangantalinga, Iba. Palauig District includes Locloc National High School, Brgy. Locloc, Palauig and Rofulo Landa National High School at Brgy. Salaza, Palauig.

Botolan District includes Bancal Integrated School, Brgy. Bancal, Bangan-Capayawan Integrated, Beneg National High School, Botolan National High School, Botoan North Integrated School, Carael Integrated School, New Taugtog National High School, Mambog Integrated School, Panan National High School, San Isidro Integrated School and Santiago Integrated School.

Instruments

The researcher-made questionnaire was the primary data collection tool in this study. It is divided into three parts. First part of the survey questionnaire part assessed the perception of the teacher-respondents on the impact of climate change to teaching. This part had a total of 70 items. The respondents answered from the scale ranging from 4 (Strongly Agree), 3 (Moderately Agree, 2 (Disagree) and 1 (Strongly Disagree).

The second part assessed the perception of the teacher-respondents on the impact of climate change to learning. This part has 70 items. The respondents answered from the scale ranging from 4 (Strongly Agree), 3 (Moderately Agree, 2 (Disagree) and 1 (Strongly Disagree).

The third part determined if there is a relationship between the impact of climate change to teaching and learning and the academic performance of the students. The respondents checked the range of the average grades of the students in the fourth quarter: (5) 90-100 Outstanding, (4) 85-89 Very Satisfactory, (3) 80-84 Satisfactory, (2) 75-79 Fairly Satisfactory, and (1) Below 75 Did Not Meet Expectation for the school year 2022-2023.

After the proposal defense, the researcher sought the pre-approval of the oral examination committee composed of Adviser (Dr. Elizabeth N. Farin), Executive Chairman (Dr. Marie Fe D. De Guzman), Chairperson (Dr. Esmen M. Cabal), Members (Dr. Thelma Q. Meer, Dr. Katherine B. Parangat) Secretary (Ms. Mary Rovian B. Bacani).

The researcher conducted a dry-run or trial among thirty (30) School Personnel who later were no longer included in the actual distribution on the instrument. In Appendix shows the results of the Cronbach's Alpha Test of Reliability.

Data Analysis

The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) computer software and MS Excel were used for the computations and interpretations of data. The statistical tools in the analysis and interpretation of data and hypotheses testing include the following.

1. Frequency Distribution. This was employed in determining the frequency counts and percentage distribution of the academic performance of students.
2. Mean. This was utilized in measuring the responses on the perceived impact of climate change in teaching in terms of classroom management, classroom activities, students' concentration, students' attendance, students' participation in class discussion, students' health, and physical infrastructure; and perceived impact of climate change in student's learning in terms of classroom management, classroom activities, students' concentration, students' attendance, students' participation in class discussion, students' health, and physical infrastructure.
3. Likert Scale. The following scale were used for the perceived impact of climate change in teaching; perceived impact of climate change in student's learning; and the academic performance of students.

Teacher's Perception towards the Impact of Climate Change in Teaching

<i>Point</i>	<i>Point Scale</i>	<i>Qualitative Interpretation</i>	<i>Symbol</i>
4	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree	SA
3	2.50-3.24	Agree	A
2	1.75-2.49	Disagree	D
1	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree	SD

Teacher's Perception towards the Impact of Climate Change in Learning

<i>Point</i>	<i>Point Scale</i>	<i>Qualitative Interpretation</i>	<i>Symbol</i>
4	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree	SA
3	2.50-3.24	Agree	A
2	1.75-2.49	Disagree	D
1	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree	SD

Academic Performance of Students

<i>Scale</i>	<i>Performance Rating</i>	<i>Qualitative Interpretation</i>	<i>Symbol</i>
5	90 – 100	Outstanding	O
4	85 – 89.99	Very Satisfactory	VS
3	80 – 84.4	Satisfactory	S
2	75 – 79.4	Fairly Satisfactory	FS
1	Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectation/Failed	F

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). In testing the significant difference of the responses when grouped according to dimensions, the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) will be used. This was used in testing difference on the perception of teachers on the impact of climate change to students learning; and testing difference on the perception of teachers on the impact of climate change on their teaching.

The ANOVA makes use of the F ratio or variance ratio. The various groups being compared are assumed to belong to a population with a normal distribution, each group randomly selected and independent from the other group. The variables from each group also have standard deviations that are approximately equal (Parreño, 2006).

Decision Rule 1: If the computed and significance value is greater or higher than ($>$) 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative.

Decision Rule 2: If the computed significance value is less or lower than ($<$) 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative.

5. Correlation Analysis. This was used to investigate the relationship (r) between the impact of climate change to teaching and learning; and testing relationship between the impact of climate to teaching and academic performance.

The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson r is the most common statistical tool in measuring the linear relationship between two random variables. This formula was developed and perfected by Karl Pearson, a colleague of Francis Galton who made behavioral studies of humans. It became the basis of different theories in the field of heredity, psychology, anthropology, and statistics. It can be used to determine the linearity of the relationships between two variables.

The following will be used to interpret result of correlation coefficient value:

Interpretation of Correlation Coefficient Value (C)

<i>Correlation Coefficient</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>	<i>Symbol</i>
± 1.000	Perfect positive or negative correlation	PC
± 0.75 to ± 0.99	Very high positive or negative correlation	VHC
± 0.50 to ± 0.74	High positive or negative correlation	HC
± 0.25 to ± 0.49	Low positive or negative correlation	LC
± 0.01 to ± 0.24	Very low positive or negative correlation	VLC
0	No correlation	NC

Results and Discussion

This section presents the gathered and processed data using tabular form, interpreted and analyzed to provide a better and clear understanding on the problems stated in Chapter 1.

1. Perceived Effects of Climate Change in Teaching

1.1. Classroom Management

Table 2 shows the perceived effects of climate change in teaching in terms of classroom management.

Table 2. *Perceived Effects of Climate Change in Teaching in terms of Classroom Management*

	<i>Classroom Management</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	Climate change affects classroom management by necessitating adaptations to accommodate extreme weather events such as heatwaves or storms	3.75	Strongly Agree	1
2	The changing climate noticeably affects the overall classroom atmosphere.	3.66	Strongly Agree	2.5
3	The changing weather patterns, attributed to climate change, disrupt classroom management practices	3.60	Strongly Agree	8
4	Climate change causes increased temperature resulting in class disruptions.	3.61	Strongly Agree	6.5
5	Warmer temperatures, as a consequence of climate change, directly influence student behavior and engagement in classroom activities	3.56	Strongly Agree	10
6	Changes in temperature and rainfall patterns due to climate change disrupt the scheduling and organization of classroom activities and routines	3.64	Strongly Agree	4
7	Extreme heat influences the behavior and engagement of students in the classroom.	3.66	Strongly Agree	2.5
8	Climate-related challenges contribute to increased stress and burnout among teachers, affecting the ability to manage the classroom effectively.	3.61	Strongly Agree	6.5
9	Climate change causes increased temperature leads to more frequent power outages, disrupting technology-dependent teaching methods and classroom management strategies.	3.57	Strongly Agree	9
10	Limited access to outdoor spaces due to climate-related factors hampers the implementation of practical and experiential learning activities.	3.62	Strongly Agree	5

Overall Weighted Mean	3.63	Strongly Agree
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The teacher-respondents strongly agreed that climate change affected classroom management by necessitating adaptations to accommodate extreme weather events such as heatwaves or storms, manifested on the highest computed recorded weighted mean of 3.75 (rank 1); while they strongly agreed that warmer temperatures, as a consequence of climate change, directly influenced student behavior and engagement in classroom activities, had the lowest weighted mean of 3.56 (rank 10).

On average, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the effects of climate change in teaching in terms of classroom management, manifested on the computed overall weighted mean of 3.63. The findings underscore that climate change and climate displacement exacerbate existing educational inequalities and barriers to education. Classroom management, rural communities, those with pre-existing health risks and persons with disabilities are the most vulnerable to climate-induced barriers to education. Climate adaptation protects students and the schools by making them less vulnerable to the effects of climate change. For example, to protect against sea level rise and increased flooding, communities might build seawalls or relocate schools to higher ground. Conversely, negative school climate can harm students and raise liability issues for schools and districts. Negative school climate is linked to lower student achievement and graduation rates, and it creates opportunities for violence, bullying, and even suicide.

This study conducted by Igu, Anochiwa, Ogba, Nwinyinya, Eze, Ogar & Ugbogu. (2023) examined how teacher’s climate change belief influences classroom management practices for students’ climate change awareness. Findings from the study revealed among other things that a teacher’s perception of climate change is a significant predictor of students’ perception of climate change. Based on the findings of the study, one of the recommendations is that Government and school administrators should encourage regular training and re-training of teachers on issues of climate change in order to deepen their beliefs on the phenomenon and thus, increase their awareness levels which will seamlessly transcend to students.

Furthermore, the most effective way of preventing heat-associated illness in children is by separating the students physically from heat and by keeping them in a cooled indoor environment. By utilizing the indoor space during extreme heat is an ideal way to protect students if a school has an alternative cooled indoor environment that can be made available for student physical activity (Arizona Department of Health Services, 2021).

1.2. Classroom Activities

The perceived effects of climate change in teaching in terms of classroom activities is shown in Table 3.

The teacher-respondents strongly agreed that climate change impacts the feasibility and safety of outdoor classroom activities due to factors such as extreme temperatures and unpredictable weather patterns, manifested on the highest computed recorded weighted mean of 3.65 (rank 1); while they strongly agreed that climate change-related disruptions in transportation and access to school facilities impact the planning and execution of extracurricular activities and special events, had the lowest weighted mean of 3.50 (rank 10).

Table 3. *Perceived Impact of Climate Change in Teaching in terms of Classroom Activities*

	<i>Classroom Activities</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	Climate change impacts the feasibility and safety of outdoor classroom activities due to factors such as extreme temperatures and unpredictable weather patterns	3.65	Strongly Agree	1
2	Extreme heat affects the availability and suitability of outdoor spaces for teaching activities.	3.60	Strongly Agree	4
3	Climate change-related events such as floods and landslides restrict the availability of outdoor spaces for educational activities, thereby impacting the diversity of learning experiences	3.61	Strongly Agree	2.5
4	Changes in temperature and rainfall patterns, influenced by climate change, disrupt planned classroom experiments or projects.	3.61	Strongly Agree	2.5
5	Severe and frequent storms, linked to climate change, necessitate adjustments to scheduled classroom activities	3.57	Strongly Agree	6.5
6	Flooding, resulting from changes in rainfall patterns, affects the ability to conduct certain classroom activities.	3.58	Strongly Agree	5
7	Disruptions in the usual balance of nature, such as deforestation and loss of biodiversity, affect the integration of environmental education into classroom activities	3.52	Strongly Agree	8
8	The heat impact the overall energy levels and enthusiasm of students in participating in classroom discussions and activities	3.51	Strongly Agree	9
9	Climate change-related disruptions in transportation and access to school facilities impact the planning and execution of extracurricular activities and special events	3.50	Strongly Agree	10
10	The effects of climate influence our overall teaching approach and the adaptability of classroom activities to the weather conditions.	3.57	Strongly Agree	6.5
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.57	Strongly Agree	

On average, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the impact of climate change in teaching in terms of classroom activities, manifested on the computed overall weighted mean of 3.57. The findings suggest that climate change can impact the education sector directly through effects related to the damage of education infrastructure; loss of education material; injury/mortality of students, teachers and parents; and psychosocial stress resulting from exposure to extreme weather events. As such, classroom activities are affected since many places have experienced changes in rainfall, resulting in more floods, droughts, or intense rain, as well as more frequent and severe heat waves. The planet's oceans and glaciers have also experienced changes—oceans are warming and becoming more acidic, ice caps are melting, and sea level is rising.

Namdar (2018) argued that global climate change (GCC) has become one of the most debated socio-scientific issues after an increase in media attention. Recently, there have also been several studies describing students' and teachers' alternative conceptions about GCC. Therefore, designing learning environments at the college level that focus on accurate conceptions of GCC has become important in order for pre-service teachers to correct their alternative conceptions. There are, however, a limited number of studies that aim to both increase pre-service teachers' knowledge about these issues and explore their perceptions of teaching this subject. Teacher education programs should integrate inquiry-based GCC instruction to increase pre-service teachers' knowledge as well as their preparedness to teach about this important planetary issue.

Wargocki, et al (2019) posit that the heat stress caused by elevated outdoor temperatures has been shown to increase the number of pupils failing to pass exams, raised classroom temperatures may also have negative consequences for the work of teachers and even on parents, who may have to stay at home or leave work early when their children cannot attend school because of sickness or disability due to suboptimal classroom conditions. Such consequences would have considerable socio-economic implications.

1.3. Students' Concentration

Table 4 presents the perceived impact of climate change in teaching in terms of students' concentration.

The teacher-respondents strongly agreed that a correlation between extreme weather events, such as heatwaves or storms, and fluctuations in students' focus and attention span during lessons, manifested on the highest computed recorded weighted mean of 3.59 (rank 1); while they strongly agreed that there were changes in temperature and rainfall patterns, influenced by climate change, result in distractions that hinder student concentration; and flooding, resulting from changes in rainfall patterns, may divert the students' focus on family problem caused by flooding, had the lowest weighted mean of 3.51 (tied at rank 9.5).

Table 4. *Perceived Impact of Climate Change in Teaching in terms of Students' Concentration*

	<i>Students' Concentration</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	A correlation between extreme weather events, such as heatwaves or storms, and fluctuations in students' focus and attention span during lessons	3.59	Strongly Agree	1
2	Warmer temperatures, as a result of climate change, contribute to difficulties in maintaining student focus during lessons	3.55	Strongly Agree	6.5
3	The rising temperatures contribute to restlessness and discomfort among students, affecting their concentration levels.	3.57	Strongly Agree	3.5
4	Changes in temperature and humidity levels due to climate change significantly affect students' cognitive abilities and academic performance	3.57	Strongly Agree	3.5
5	The increased heat contribute to fatigue among students, affecting their concentration levels throughout the school day.	3.58	Strongly Agree	2
6	Changes in temperature and rainfall patterns, influenced by climate change, result in distractions that hinder student concentration	3.51	Strongly Agree	9.5
7	Climate change-related factors influence students' ability to engage with lesson content and maintain focus during instructional time	3.54	Strongly Agree	8
8	Climate change-related challenges affect the implementation of effective teaching strategies that require sustained student concentration	3.55	Strongly Agree	6.5
9	Flooding, resulting from changes in rainfall patterns, may divert the students' focus on family problem caused by flooding.	3.51	Strongly Agree	9.5
10	The effects of climate change necessitate adjustments to teaching methods and approaches to better support students' concentration in the classroom.	3.56	Strongly Agree	5
<i>Overall Weighted Mean</i>		3.55	Strongly Agree	

On average, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the impact of climate change in teaching in terms of students' concentration, manifested on the computed overall weighted mean of 3.55. The findings imply that storms have a disruptive impact on education. In areas severely affected by winds, children are more likely to accumulate an educational delay and less likely to complete education. On the other hand, heat-related illnesses can include muscle cramps, heat exhaustion—which may come with nausea, vomiting, fatigue, and fever—and heat stroke, which in extreme cases can lead to seizures or even death. A warming climate can contribute to the intensity of heat waves by increasing the chances of very hot days and nights. Climate warming also increases evaporation on land, which can worsen drought and create conditions more prone to wildfire and a longer wildfire season. Thus, a significant negative effect of heat and cold on students' test scores. Along with adverse ramifications on students' academic performance and learning capacity, prolonged exposure to hot environments can also bring about health symptoms of exhaustion and dehydration.

Shepardson, Niyogi, Roychoudhury & Hirsch (2022) stated that today there is much interest in teaching students about climate change. Much of this effort has focused directly on students' understanding of climate change. They hypothesize, however, that in order for students to understand climate change they must first understand climate as a system and how changes to this system due to both natural and human influences result in climatic and environmental changes and feedbacks. By articulating a draft conceptual progression based on students' conceptions and our climate system framework as a means to inform curriculum development, instructional design, and future research in climate and environmental education.

The study of Haverinen-Shaughnessy and Shaughnessy (2015) found a significant positive association between ventilation rates and mathematics scores, particularly when high ventilation rates were excluded as outliers. Additionally, there was an increase in mathematics scores for each liter per second per person increase in ventilation rate and a further increase with each 1°C decrease in temperature within a certain range. The study concludes that adequate ventilation and maintaining thermal comfort in classrooms can significantly improve students' academic performance.

1.4. Students' Attendance

The perceived impact of climate change in teaching in terms of students' attendance is presented in Table 5.

The teacher-respondents strongly agreed that the increased occurrence of extreme weather events, such as floods and droughts, due to climate change, poses challenges for students' attendance, manifested on the highest computed recorded weighted mean of 3.60 (rank 1); while they strongly agreed that there are observable challenges due to extreme heat impact students' willingness to attend school regularly, had the lowest weighted mean of 3.41 (rank 10).

Table 5. *Perceived Impact of Climate Change in Teaching in terms of Students' Attendance*

<i>Students' Attendance</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1 The increased occurrence of extreme weather events, such as floods and droughts, due to climate change, poses challenges for students' attendance	3.60	Strongly Agree	1
2 Warmer temperatures, resulting from climate change, contribute to higher rates of student absenteeism	3.43	Strongly Agree	8.5
3 There are observable challenges due to extreme heat impact students' willingness to attend school regularly.	3.41	Strongly Agree	10
4 Temperature and rainfall patterns, influenced by climate change, result in transportation difficulties for students, affecting their attendance.	3.43	Strongly Agree	8.5
5 Severe and frequent storms, linked to climate change, impact students' ability to attend school regularly and sometimes due to cancellation of classes.	3.52	Strongly Agree	3
6 Flooding, resulting from changes in rainfall patterns, contributes to students' absence from school	3.47	Strongly Agree	5
7 There is an increased health risk due to extreme heat or sudden rainfall that results to absenteeism	3.57	Strongly Agree	2
8 The destruction of homes and displacement of families, caused by climate-related disasters affect student attendance	3.46	Strongly Agree	6
9 Climate change-related factors influence students' and parents' decisions to attend or skip school, considering the increased frequency of natural disasters	3.50	Strongly Agree	4
10 The effects of climate change impact the overall attendance trends and patterns among students across various grade levels.	3.45	Strongly Agree	7
Overall Weighted Mean	3.48	Strongly Agree	

On average, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the impact of climate change in teaching in terms of students' attendance, manifested on the computed overall weighted mean of 3.48. The findings manifest on the increased incidence of weather-related diseases such as malaria and diarrhoea caused by climate change can render children too weak to attend school. Children miss classes because of ill health and, worse still, can be withdrawn from school altogether. The worst affected are those of primary school age. Dealing with climate change is a complex system change to students' attendance in school. Climate change coping strategies include things like taking environmentally responsible actions, this is a potent way to manage and reduce the anxiety; adopting a problem-solving attitude; cognitive re-structuring or reframing; social support-seeking; becoming more attentive to the issue, expressive coping.

Relatively, Sakız (2017) reported outcomes of a school-based program aiming to promote achievement, attendance and positive perceptions towards the climate change and social-emotional adaptation among students with disabilities (SWD). The program included a series of training and social activities for school staff, parents and children followed by implementation of the knowledge gained through these activities. The program lasted one school year and data were collected through quantitative and qualitative methods. Results of the study indicated enhanced student attendance and achievement, social-emotional development, and positive perceptions about climate change. In addition, parents and teachers were mostly content with development of students and the attempts of their schools to prompt student learning. Findings of this research indicate the significance of the holistic approach in educating students in

mainstream schools and confirm that schools can make progress relying on their internal structures and planned action.

1.5. Students' Participation in Class Discussion

Table 6 shows the perceived impact of climate change in teaching in terms of students' participation in class discussion.

The teacher-respondents strongly agreed that climate change-induced weather patterns disrupt usual class dynamics, affecting students' willingness to actively participate in discussions; rising temperatures impact the overall energy and attentiveness of students during class discussions; severe and frequent storms, linked to climate change, impact class discussions on disaster preparedness and resilience; and the challenges posed by of climate change impact the quality and depth of students' participation in class discussions across various subjects, manifested on the highest computed recorded weighted mean of 3.50 (tied at rank 2.5); while they strongly agreed that climate change-related challenges influence students' willingness to actively contribute to class conversations; and the sudden heavy rain led to a decrease in students' enthusiasm and involvement in classroom discussions, had the lowest weighted mean of 3.41 (tied at rank 9.5).

Table 6. *Perceived Impact of Climate Change in Teaching in terms of Students' Participation in Class Discussion*

	<i>Students' Participation in Class Discussion</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	Observed that climate change-induced weather patterns disrupt usual class dynamics, affecting students' willingness to actively participate in discussions	3.50	Strongly Agree	2.5
2	Climate change-related challenges influence students' willingness to actively contribute to class conversations	3.41	Strongly Agree	9.5
3	The rising temperatures impact the overall energy and attentiveness of students during class discussions.	3.50	Strongly Agree	2.5
4	The sudden heavy rain led to a decrease in students' enthusiasm and involvement in classroom discussions.	3.41	Strongly Agree	9.5
5	Severe and frequent storms, linked to climate change, impact class discussions on disaster preparedness and resilience	3.50	Strongly Agree	2.5
6	The heat-related discomfort impact students' ability to express their thoughts and ideas actively in class discussions.	3.47	Strongly Agree	6
7	Floods, droughts and heat spells, exacerbated by climate change, lead to more discussions on climate adaptation and mitigation strategies in the classroom	3.48	Strongly Agree	5
8	Changes in temperature and rainfall patterns, associated with climate change, prompt more discussions about weather-related phenomena and their implications.	3.45	Strongly Agree	8
9	The students' perception of climate change-related challenges affects their overall engagement in collaborative and group discussions.	3.46	Strongly Agree	7

On average, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the impact of climate change in teaching in terms of students' participation in class discussion, manifested on the computed overall weighted mean of 3.47. The findings suggest that climate change impacted classroom ambient temperature which has a significant impact on student performance. Lower temperatures, around 20-22 °C, are associated with better cognitive performance, including memory, verbal comprehension, and reasoning. More likely, classroom climate is a perceived quality of the setting. It emerges in a somewhat fluid state from the complex transaction of many immediate environmental factors. Studying the climate helps us predict how much rain the next winter might bring, or how far sea levels will rise due to warmer sea temperatures. Climate change may be affected by extreme weather, or which effective discussions inside the classrooms are threatened by climate change. An academic environment which might be impacted by climate change can fosters a sense of belonging, perception of competence, and offers student autonomy, will result in increased motivation to learn.

Nation and Feldman (2021) highlighted that climate change is complex and controversial in nature, yet seen by educators and policymakers as an important topic to be taught within secondary science education. Teachers' beliefs about the instruction of climate change are unclear. The presence of controversy can influence teachers' instructional decisions causing confusion about the science of climate change. Therefore, the role of teachers' beliefs must be considered when examining their instruction. The study examined the complex nature of science teacher beliefs about climate change instruction, their practice, and the impact on student outcomes within four marine science classrooms over the course of one semester. Findings suggest teachers have strong beliefs about the anthropogenic causes and implications of climate change, high levels of concern for future generations, and value climate change education. Yet, the controversial nature of the topic, current political climate, and resistance from stakeholders inhibited teachers from espousing these beliefs within their instruction.

The study of Alberto, Jiao and Zhang (2021) displayed the results of the primary specification for college and high school students wherein several findings emerge. Firstly, extreme temperatures, regardless of cold or hot, can induce an education-leisure trade-off whereas time spent on all other activities shows no response to such weather extremes. This trade-off holds for both high school and college students. Secondly, the heterogeneous effects of temperature among students are remarkable. College students tend to reduce class attendance and class time on cold days and they also decrease their involvement and time allocation on self-study during scorching days. Conversely, high school students respond to temperature through a different mechanism.

1.6. Students' Health

The perceived impact of climate change in teaching in terms of students' health is shown in Table 7.

The teacher-respondents strongly agreed that climate change-related challenges influence students' susceptibility to illnesses, such as respiratory issues or allergies, manifested on the highest computed recorded weighted mean of 3.57 (rank 1); while they strongly agreed that increased heat brought by climate change contributed to challenges in maintaining proper nutrition and hydration among students; and the students' perception of climate change-related challenges impacts their adherence to health and safety guidelines, such as wearing appropriate clothing and staying hydrated, had the lowest weighted mean of 3.44 (tied at rank 9.5).

Table 7. *Perceived Impact of Climate Change in Teaching in terms of Students' Health*

	<i>Students' Health</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	There are disparities in students' health outcomes based on socio-economic factors or geographic location, particularly in relation to climate change-related health risks	3.50	Strongly Agree	3.5
2	Warmer temperatures, resulting from climate change, affect students' susceptibility to heat-related illnesses such as heatstroke and dehydration	3.47	Strongly Agree	6
3	Climate change-related challenges influence students' susceptibility to illnesses, such as respiratory issues or allergies.	3.57	Strongly Agree	1
4	Changes in temperature and rainfall patterns, associated with climate change, affect the availability and affordability of food items commonly consumed by students	3.46	Strongly Agree	7.5
5	Scarcity of water and drought at home or in school, caused by climate change, impact students' access to clean drinking water and sanitation facilities, thereby affecting their health	3.48	Strongly Agree	5
6	Increased heat brought by climate change contributes to challenges in maintaining proper nutrition and hydration among students	3.44	Strongly Agree	9.5
7	Changes in temperature and rainfall patterns, associated with climate change, contribute to the spread of vector-borne diseases and respiratory illnesses among students	3.46	Strongly Agree	7.5
8	Severe and frequent storms, linked to climate change, affect students' physical safety and well-being during extreme weather events	3.51	Strongly Agree	2
9	The students' perception of climate change-related challenges impacts their adherence to health and safety guidelines, such as wearing appropriate clothing and staying hydrated.	3.44	Strongly Agree	9.5
10	Proactive measures are necessary to address the impact of climate change on student health and ensure their overall well-being in educational settings	3.50	Strongly Agree	3.5
Overall Weighted Mean		3.48	Strongly Agree	

On average, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the impact of climate change in teaching in terms of students' health, manifested on the computed overall weighted mean of 3.48. The findings imply that climate change represents a major threat to students' respiratory conditions, through several different direct and indirect pathways, including the increase in temperature, increase in ozone exposure, prolonged aeroallergen seasons and introduction of aeroallergens to new areas. Extreme weather events reduce the availability of safe drinking water, compromise sanitation and increase the incidence of weather-related diseases such as malaria and diarrhea diseases, leading to absenteeism and possible withdrawal of children from school. Climate change worsen existing air pollution. Exposure to these pollutants can lead to or worsen health problems, such as respiratory and heart diseases. Climate change can also affect indoor air quality. Increases in outside air pollutants, such as ozone and particulate matter, could lead to higher indoor exposures.

According to Osama, Brindley, Majeed, Murray, Shah, Toumazos & Meinert (2018) the observed and projected impacts of climate change on human health are significant. While climate change has gathered global momentum and is taught frequently, the extent to which the relationships between climate change and health are taught remains uncertain. Education provides an opportunity to create public engagement on these issues, but the extent to which historical implementation of climate health education could be leveraged is not well understood.

Bidassey-Manilal, Wright, Engelbrecht, Albers, Garland and Matoane (2016) stated that exposure to high temperatures has known adverse effects on human health. These effects may be especially dare yet to be fully operationalized. Heat-related health impacts may be mild, such as nausea, headache and dizziness, or extreme, including vomiting, heat stroke and cardiac arrest. headache, fatigue and "feeling very hot" were the most common symptoms experienced by Cameroonian schoolchildren when indoor classroom air temperature was high (no threshold was defined).

1.7. Physical Infrastructure

Table 8 presents the perceived impact of climate change in teaching in terms of physical infrastructure.

The teacher-respondents strongly agreed that the destruction of infrastructure, such as school buildings and roads, due to climate-related disasters, poses challenges to the continuity of teaching and learning activities, manifested on the highest computed recorded weighted mean of 3.50 (rank 1); while they strongly agreed that changing weather patterns attributed to climate change contribute to the deterioration of school buildings and facilities; and changing climate pose challenges to the maintenance and sustainability of school buildings and facilities, had the lowest weighted mean of 3.41 (tied at rank 9.5).

Table 8. *Perceived Impact of Climate Change in Teaching in terms of Physical Infrastructure*

	<i>Physical Infrastructure</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	Changing weather patterns attributed to climate change contribute to the deterioration of school buildings and facilities	3.41	Strongly Agree	9.5
2	Changing climate pose challenges to the maintenance and sustainability of school buildings and facilities	3.41	Strongly Agree	9.5
3	Changes in temperature and rainfall patterns due to climate change impact the resilience of school infrastructure to withstand extreme weather events	3.44	Strongly Agree	6
4	The challenges posed by changing climate impact the availability and accessibility of shaded outdoor areas for students and teachers	3.46	Strongly Agree	3.5
5	Severe and frequent storms, flooding, and landslides, attributed to climate change, impact the structural integrity and safety of school buildings and facilities	3.45	Strongly Agree	5
6	The climate change contributes to challenges in maintaining a comfortable and conducive learning environment within classrooms and common areas	3.46	Strongly Agree	3.5
7	The destruction of infrastructure, such as school buildings and roads, due to climate-related disasters, poses challenges to the continuity of teaching and learning activities	3.50	Strongly Agree	1
8	The vulnerability of school infrastructure to climate change-related hazards impact the overall learning environment for students	3.48	Strongly Agree	2
9	Notices any disparities in the resilience of school infrastructure to climate change-related hazards based on geographic location, socio-economic status, or other factors.	3.43	Strongly Agree	7.5
10	The effects of climate change impact the overall quality and adaptability of physical infrastructure to meet the changing needs of teaching in a sustainable manner	3.43	Strongly Agree	7.5
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.45	Strongly Agree	

On average, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the impact of climate change in teaching in terms of physical infrastructure, manifested on the computed overall weighted mean of 3.45. The findings imply that good infrastructure of school not only will a well-built facility provide a safe working environment for teachers and students alike during changes in climate, it will also entice teachers to join the teaching staff and to stay. Proper facilities give teachers and students a safe space to teach as well as one that is beneficial for their physical and emotional health. Damage to school infrastructures such as health, communications or transportation can create conditions of further vulnerability for people as damaged infrastructure may reduce access to certain resources or income-generating activities, making them less resilient to new and emerging risks.

Ng (2021) considered that climate change impacts are the consequences of climate change for natural and human systems. Many natural systems are affected by regional climate change, particularly temperature increases. Observed impacts include sea level rise; changes in snow, ice, and permafrost; effects on hydrological systems, including precipitation, floods and droughts, tropical cyclones, storms, and wave heights; changes on terrestrial biological systems; changes in marine and freshwater biological systems associated with rising water temperatures and stratification; and ocean changes in ice cover, salinity, acidity, oxygen levels, and circulation. These physical impacts of climate change have different implications for different cities, regions, and countries across the world. They also pose various challenges to multiple sectors, such as energy, water, or food supply, transport, sanitation, and telecommunications, and each with its own.

The study of Mokaya (2013) found that improved academic achievement is associated with more adequate and well-spaced classrooms, adequate and ample spacing in the libraries, adequate science laboratories, adequate water and sanitation facilities and adequate participation in co-curricular activities.

1.8. Summary: Perceived Impact of Climate Change in Teaching

The summary on the perceived impact of climate change in teaching is presented in Table 9.

Table 9. *Summary on the Perceived Impact of Climate Change in Teaching*

	<i>Dimensions</i>	<i>Overall Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	Classroom Management	3.63	Strongly Agree	1

2	Classroom Activities	3.57	Strongly Agree	2
3	Students' Concentration	3.55	Strongly Agree	3
4	Students' Attendance	3.48	Strongly Agree	4.5
5	Students' Participation in Class Discussion	3.47	Strongly Agree	6
6	Students' Health	3.48	Strongly Agree	4.5
7	Physical Infrastructure	3.45	Strongly Agree	7
Grand Mean		3.52	Strongly Agree	

It can be noted that the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the impact of climate change in teaching in terms of classroom management, with the highest computed mean of 3.63 (rank 1). This is followed by the impact of climate change in teaching in terms of classroom activities, with computed mean of 3.57 (rank 2); students' concentration, with computed mean of 3.55 (rank 3); students' attendance; and students' health, with computed mean of 3.48 (tied at rank 4.5); students' participation in class discussion, with computed mean of 3.47 (rank 6); and physical infrastructure, had the lowest computed mean of 3.45 (rank 7).

On average, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the impact of climate change in teaching, manifested on the computed grand mean of 3.52.

It is interesting to note that climate change impacted classroom management of teachers in the school system. Climate change and climate displacement exacerbate existing educational inequalities and barriers to education. A mandate of schools will be to provide the skills and abilities needed to survive and thrive in a depleted ecosystem. For all but a scarce collection of indigenous and alternative cultural groups, new ways of thinking and living which are not presently realized must be invented and learned, or perhaps re-learned, to achieve global sustainability. In other words, education systems must do for future generations what they did not do for us. Schooling as we know it requires a wholesale transformation. In the context of global warming, schools play dual roles. On one hand, schools can be a powerful tool in the fight against climate change. On the other hand, they are also in the crosshairs of becoming another casualty of climate change. Without considerable safeguarding, the ability of institutions of learning to continue effective operation is threatened. There is a vast literature covering engineering and material solutions to prepare schools for a changing climate. These solutions include utilizing renewable energy sources, providing students with electronics for online instruction, and hardening structures against storms, fires, floods, mold, heatwaves, and so on. Despite the advantages that re-engineering campuses may bring, disruptions to the learning environment can still be expected. Even the best engineering may be overwhelmed by the capricious forces of nature.

Monroe, Plate, Oxarart, Bowers & Chaves (2019) stressed that there is an increased interest in climate change education and the growing recognition of the challenges inherent to addressing this issue create an opportunity to conduct a systematic review to understand what research can contribute to our ideas about effective climate change education. Two themes were identified that are common to most environmental education: focusing on personally relevant and meaningful information and using active and engaging teaching methods. Four themes specific to issues such as climate change were also generated: engaging in deliberative discussions, interacting with scientists, addressing misconceptions, and implementing school or community projects. Suggestions for addressing controversial topics like climate change are offered.

2. Perceived Impact of Climate Change in Student's Learning

2.1. Classroom Management

Table 10 shows the perceived impact of climate change in student's learning in terms of classroom management.

The teacher-respondents strongly agreed that the effects of climate change impact the overall effectiveness of our classroom management strategies to create a comfortable and conducive learning environment, manifested on the highest computed recorded weighted mean of 3.60 (rank 1); while they strongly agreed that interruptions caused by climate change-related events impact students' ability to engage effectively in classroom activities, had the lowest weighted mean of 3.51 (rank 10).

Table 10. *Perceived Impact of Climate Change in Student's Learning in terms of Classroom Management*

	<i>Classroom Management</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	The climate change affects our classroom management strategies to address the challenges posed by high temperatures and particularly in terms of disruptions caused by extreme weather events such as floods also affects the learning process.	3.57	Strongly Agree	4
2	The rising temperature impact our ability to maintain a conducive and focused learning environment in the classroom	3.56	Strongly Agree	6.5
3	Climate-related emergencies, like storms or floods disrupt the execution of planned classroom lessons and activities	3.53	Strongly Agree	8
4	There is a correlation between climate change-related environmental disruptions and challenges in maintaining classroom order and discipline	3.52	Strongly Agree	9
5	Interruptions caused by climate change-related events impact students' ability to engage effectively in classroom activities.	3.51	Strongly Agree	10
6	Infrastructure damages caused by climate change, like destruction of school buildings and roads, impact the logistical aspects of classroom management	3.57	Strongly Agree	4

7	Climate-related emergencies, such as evacuations due to heavy rains and flooding, influence the planning and execution of classroom activities.	3.58	Strongly Agree	2
8	Climate-related concerns, such as the spread of diseases or health issues exacerbated by extreme weather, impact the implementation of classroom management strategies	3.56	Strongly Agree	6.5
9	The proactive measures, such as disaster preparedness training and environmental education, can improve classroom management in the face of climate change-related challenges	3.57	Strongly Agree	4
10	The effects of climate change impact the overall effectiveness of our classroom management strategies to create a comfortable and conducive learning environment.	3.60	Strongly Agree	1
Overall Weighted Mean		3.56	Strongly Agree	

On average, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the impact of climate change in student’s learning in terms of classroom management, manifested on the computed overall weighted mean of 3.56. The findings suggest in creating an environment for students that allows them to learn without distractions. Reduces poor behaviour and distractions so students are focused on learning. Facilitates social and emotional development. Students who are in a well-managed classroom are more likely to feel comfortable and connected to activities occurring in class and elsewhere in the school. Students can more easily connect with their peers, building relationships and strengthening social and emotional learning in addition to academic achievement.

According to Okoye & Omenyi (2023) that the classroom teachers are at the centre of the classroom activities because they are the ones who turn various educational policies into practice under a classroom setting. To ensure that quality education is provided to the students, classroom teachers are expected to manage the classroom effectively. This is because the classroom is where the actual teaching and learning activities take place and where all the educational policies and programmes are implemented. The classroom is the meeting point for both teachers and students where curricular activities are implemented. The classroom is essentially the focal point for educational instruction and as such should be an environment conducive to quality teaching and learning. The extent to which this is achieved greatly depends on how the classroom is being managed. Classroom management comes into play when a teacher tactfully directs students’ activities, available educational resources and time constraint in such a way that the desired objectives are achieved.

2.2. Classroom Activities

The perceived impact of climate change in student’s learning in terms of classroom activities is shown in Table 11.

The teacher-respondents strongly agreed that climate change impacts classroom activities, considering factors such as extreme weather events and infrastructure damage, manifested on the highest computed recorded weighted mean of 3.58 (rank 1); while they strongly agreed that climate change necessitate adjustments to classroom management techniques to address disruptions caused by weather-related factors, had the lowest weighted mean of 3.45 (rank 10).

Table 11. *Perceived Impact of Climate Change in Student’s Learning in terms of Classroom Activities*

	<i>Classroom Activities</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	Climate change impacts classroom activities, considering factors such as extreme weather events and infrastructure damage	3.58	Strongly Agree	1
2	The increased heat impact the engagement and participation levels of students in hands-on or interactive classroom activities.	3.49	Strongly Agree	5
3	Changing climate pose challenges to maintaining a well-organized and disciplined classroom environment	3.53	Strongly Agree	2.5
4	Climate change-related factors, such as warmer temperatures and changing weather patterns, impact the effectiveness of classroom activities	3.46	Strongly Agree	8
5	Disruptions caused by climate change, such as storms or infrastructure damage, hinder the execution of classroom activities	3.53	Strongly Agree	2.5
6	Challenges posed by climate change affect the implementation of classroom rules and routines	3.46	Strongly Agree	8
7	The heat-related stress impact the effectiveness of technology-based activities or multimedia presentations in the classroom	3.46	Strongly Agree	8
8	Adapt classroom activities to accommodate interruptions caused by climate change-related events, such as extreme heat or heavy rainfall	3.48	Strongly Agree	6
9	Climate change necessitate adjustments to classroom management techniques to address disruptions caused by weather-related factors	3.45	Strongly Agree	10
10	Climate-related concerns, such as health risks associated with extreme heat or air pollution, influence the selection and design of classroom activities.	3.50	Strongly Agree	4
Overall Weighted Mean		3.49	Strongly Agree	

On average, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the impact of climate change in student’s learning in terms of classroom activities, manifested on the computed overall weighted mean of 3.49. The findings underscore that poor performance of students due

to absenteeism and concentration might hinder their outputs in the school system. This is due to climate change and environmental problems faced by students.

Karpudewan, Roth & Abdullah (2015) stated that climate change generally and global warming specifically have become a common feature of the daily news. Due to widespread recognition of the adverse consequences of climate change on human lives, concerted societal effort has been taken to address it by means of the curriculum. This study was designed to test the effect that child-centered classroom activities affected by climate change. This was used to measure the effectiveness of these activities on increasing children's knowledge about global warming; changing their attitudes to be more favourable towards the environment and identify the relationship between knowledge and attitude that exist in this study. Statistically significant differences in favour of the treatment group were detected for both knowledge and environmental attitudes. Non-significant relationship was identified between knowledge and attitude in this study. Interviews with randomly selected students from treatment and comparison groups further underscore these findings.

2.3. Students' Concentration

Table 12 presents the perceived impact of climate change in student's learning in terms of students' concentration.

The teacher-respondents strongly agreed that they observed a noticeable difference in student concentration during periods of extreme weather events, such as storms or heatwaves, attributed to climate change, manifested on the highest computed recorded weighted mean of 3.54 (rank 1); while they strongly agreed that the climate change-related factors influence the use of strategies to enhance students' concentration, such as breaks or flexible learning approaches, had the lowest weighted mean of 3.45 (rank 10).

Table 12. *Perceived Impact of Climate Change in Student's Learning in terms of Students' Concentration*

	<i>Students' Concentration</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	Observe a noticeable difference in student concentration during periods of extreme weather events, such as storms or heatwaves, attributed to climate change.	3.54	Strongly Agree	1
2	The disruptions caused by climate change, such as floods or landslides, impact students' focus and attention during learning activities	3.51	Strongly Agree	4
3	Climate-induced events like heavy rain or extreme heat contribute to students' difficulty in maintaining concentration in the classroom	3.53	Strongly Agree	2.5
4	Addressing climate change-related concerns, such as access to clean water or mitigating heat-related illnesses, can positively impact student concentration levels	3.49	Strongly Agree	5.5
5	Adapt teaching strategies to address fluctuations in student concentration levels due to climate change-related challenges	3.47	Strongly Agree	8.5
6	Proactive measures of schools and educators can be implemented to support students in maintaining focus and concentration amidst climate change-related disruptions.	3.53	Strongly Agree	2.5
7	The heat-related impact students' overall cognitive performance and concentration on academic tasks.	3.48	Strongly Agree	7
8	The climate change-related factors influence the use of strategies to enhance students' concentration, such as breaks or flexible learning approaches.	3.45	Strongly Agree	10
9	The students' perception of climate change-related challenges impacts their ability to concentrate on learning activities and assessments.	3.47	Strongly Agree	8.5
10	The effects of climate change impact the overall learning experience by affecting students' concentration and focus throughout the school day.	3.49	Strongly Agree	5.5
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.50	Strongly Agree	

On average, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the impact of climate change in student's learning in terms of students' concentration, manifested on the computed overall weighted mean of 3.50. The findings imply that along with adverse ramifications on students' academic performance and learning capacity, prolonged exposure to hot environments can also bring about health symptoms of exhaustion and dehydration. Heat-related illnesses can include muscle cramps, heat exhaustion—which may come with nausea, vomiting, fatigue, and fever—and heat stroke, which in extreme cases can lead to seizures. The increased incidence of weather related diseases such as malaria and diarrhoea caused by climate change can render children too weak to attend school. Children miss classes because of ill health and, worse still, can be withdrawn from school altogether. The worst affected are those of primary school age.

The results of the study conducted by Nam & Ito (2021) showed that even if individual students had a different level of background knowledge of climate change and human interactions, their content knowledge improved and concentration adjusted during the changes in climate. These changes have relevant to their everyday lives and current socioeconomic issues related to climate change.

Anggraini and Patmanthara (2017) stated that an effective learning condition is a condition that is truly conducive and supports the smoothness and continuity of the teaching and learning process. The learning environment is one of the learning resources that affect student learning outcomes and in the learning process. The learning environment includes the condition of school buildings, classrooms,

which have an influence on learning activities, teacher-student relationships must be well established, student facilities are adequate, adequate facilities and infrastructure can support learning activities.

2.4. Students' Attendance

The perceived impact of climate change in student's learning in terms of students' attendance is presented in Table 13.

The teacher-respondents strongly agreed that due to climate change-induced factors, such as warmer temperatures and altered weather patterns, students' attendance rates in schools is affected, manifested on the highest computed recorded weighted mean of 3.55 (rank 1); while they strongly agreed that they observed correlation between extreme weather events, such as floods or heatwaves attributed to climate change, and fluctuations in student attendance, had the lowest weighted mean of 3.44 (rank 10).

Table 13. *Perceived Impact of Climate Change in Student's Learning in terms of Students' Attendance*

	Students' Attendance	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Rank
1	Due to climate change-induced factors, such as warmer temperatures and altered weather patterns, students' attendance rates in schools is affected	3.55	Strongly Agree	1
2	The increased heat during the dry hot season contribute to a decrease in students' attendance and punctuality	3.46	Strongly Agree	9
3	Observed correlation between extreme weather events, such as floods or heatwaves attributed to climate change, and fluctuations in student attendance	3.44	Strongly Agree	10
4	The disruptions in infrastructure caused by climate change, such as road closures or damage to school buildings, impact student attendance	3.48	Strongly Agree	6
5	Perceives the role of climate change-related factors in influencing absenteeism among students, considering aspects like health concerns or transportation difficulties	3.50	Strongly Agree	3.5
6	The shifts in weather patterns and natural disasters triggered by climate change contribute to changes in student attendance patterns	3.47	Strongly Agree	7.5
7	Changing climate necessitate adjustments to school policies to address potential disruptions in student attendance due to weather-related factors	3.47	Strongly Agree	7.5
8	Addressing climate change-related challenges, such as water scarcity or extreme temperatures, can positively impact student attendance rates	3.49	Strongly Agree	5
9	Observes regional disparities in student attendance rates due to climate change-related factors, such as geographical vulnerability or access to resources	3.50	Strongly Agree	3.5
10	The proactive measures of schools and educators can be implemented to mitigate the impact of climate change on student attendance that influence learning of competencies required.	3.54	Strongly Agree	2
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.49	Strongly Agree	

On average, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the impact of climate change in student's learning in terms of students' attendance, manifested on the computed overall weighted mean of 3.49. The findings imply that climate-change-induced school disruptions can be expected to replicate and even magnify many of the same negative impacts resulting to student's attendance. Humanity will face the risks of learning loss, economic loss, and scarcity of vital resources again. Climate change has illuminated that those burdens will not be equally distributed across socio-economic classes. Economically disadvantaged and marginalized communities already face the worst impacts of climate change, and there is no reason to expect this trend to change. Although communities worldwide presently lack the technology, resources, and political will to reverse climate change directly in the short to medium term, the technologies of teaching needed to overcome expected learning losses are available and scalable now. The time to accomplish this monumental task is short. At worst, urgent action to reform how we teach, where we teach, and what we teach may allow us to offset learning losses. At best, doing so will transition education systems from being victims of climate change to becoming among the most powerful tools in the fight against it.

The study conducted by Fuller, Clee, Njabo, Tróchez, Morgan, Meñe & Smith (2018) found out climate warming are predicted to be high but coincide with an area with low adaptive capacity, thus resulted to high absenteeism of students in schooling due to accessibility and transportation.

Mc Cormack (2023) stated that climate change is expected to increase temperatures and the variability in the climate system, exposing students to hot temperatures more frequently, which may widen disparities in disciplinary referrals for those who can less easily adapt to these conditions. Heat-induced increases in behavioral referrals offer a channel for the observed relationship between heat and worse academic outcomes and highlight a possible benefit of improving school infrastructure.

2.5. Students' Participation in Class Discussion

Table 14 shows the perceived impact of climate change in student's learning in terms of students' participation in class discussion.

The teacher-respondents strongly agreed that integrating discussions about climate change impacted into classroom dialogue to enhance student participation and comprehension, manifested on the highest computed recorded weighted mean of 3.52 (rank 1); while they

strongly agreed that heat-related stress impact the overall dynamics and effectiveness of student participation in class discussions, had the lowest weighted mean of 3.40 (rank 10).

Table 14. *Perceived Impact of Climate Change in Student's Learning in terms of Students' Participation in Class Discussion*

	<i>Students' Participation in Class Discussion</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	The climate change-induced factors impact students' willingness to participate in class discussions, considering phenomena like warmer temperatures and altered weather patterns	3.42	Strongly Agree	7
2	The increased heat impact the willingness of students to actively contribute to class discussions and leads to more effective learning.	3.44	Strongly Agree	5.5
3	Climate change-related challenges like extreme heat and sudden heavy rain affect students' enthusiasm and engagement in classroom conversations.	3.46	Strongly Agree	4
4	The challenges posed increased in temperature impact the overall quality and quantity of student participation in class discussions	3.44	Strongly Agree	5.5
5	The disruptions caused by climate change, such as infrastructure damage or heat waves, influence student involvement in class discussions.	3.47	Strongly Agree	2.5
6	Climate-related challenges like water scarcity or extreme temperatures impact students' ability to participate actively in classroom discourse	3.41	Strongly Agree	8.5
7	Heat-related stress impact the overall dynamics and effectiveness of student participation in class discussions	3.40	Strongly Agree	10
8	Climate change impacts, such as floods or landslides, can positively influence student engagement in class discussions	3.41	Strongly Agree	8.5
9	Envisioned integrating discussions about climate change impacts into classroom dialogue to enhance student participation and comprehension	3.52	Strongly Agree	1
10	The effects of climate change impact the overall student involvement and contribution to class discussions across various subjects.	3.47	Strongly Agree	2.5
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.44	Strongly Agree	

On average, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the impact of climate change in student's learning in terms of students' participation in class discussion, manifested on the computed overall weighted mean of 3.44. The findings suggest that individual stories of students can forge an emotive connection, get the audience to care, and make shared global challenges seem less daunting. Discussions on climate change refers to long-term shifts in temperatures and weather patterns. Such shifts can be natural, due to changes in the sun's activity or large volcanic eruptions. Climate change may affect our health and wellbeing through the impacts of extreme events, worsening air quality, changes in the spread of infectious diseases, threats to food and water quality and quantity and effects on our mental health.

According to Wise (2020) that the patterns of responses in instruction, knowledge gaps, and a lack of learning experiences for teachers documented suggest that participation of students in discussion in the classroom decreases as an effect of climate change and learning disturbances.

In another study by Alley (2023) two classes of 10-12 year old students took two math and literacy tests in different classroom temperatures. Their scores were significantly better when the classroom temperature was 68 degrees versus 77 degrees.

2.6. Students' Health

The perceived impact of climate change in student's learning in terms of students' health is shown in Table 15.

The teacher-respondents strongly agreed that extreme heat has a direct impact on the overall health and well-being of students in your school, manifested on the highest computed recorded weighted mean of 3.63 (rank 1); while they strongly agreed that the socio-economic factors influenced by climate change, such as food insecurity or inadequate shelter, impact students' physical health and learning experiences, had the lowest weighted mean of 3.50 (rank 10).

Table 15. *Perceived Impact of Climate Change in Student's Learning in terms of Students' Health*

	<i>Students' Health</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	Extreme heat has a direct impact on the overall health and well-being of students in your school	3.63	Strongly Agree	1
2	The increased heat contribute to a noticeable decline in the general health of students, such as an increase in illnesses or health complaints	3.56	Strongly Agree	6
3	Increased heat contribute to easy spoilage of foods that students consume thus making them vulnerable to food poisoning or stomach ache.	3.57	Strongly Agree	3.5
4	The disruptions caused by climate change, such as infrastructure damage or air pollution, affect students' health and ability to learn	3.51	Strongly Agree	8.5

5	The socio-economic factors influenced by climate change, such as food insecurity or inadequate shelter, impact students' physical health and learning experiences	3.50	Strongly Agree	10
6	The climate change contributes to challenges in maintaining proper nutrition, hydration, and overall health among students	3.57	Strongly Agree	3.5
7	The heat-related stress and illnesses due to climate change impact students' ability to concentrate, engage in learning activities, and overall academic performance	3.51	Strongly Agree	8.5
8	Climate change-induced environmental stressors directly affect students' physical health in the context of learning	3.56	Strongly Agree	6
9	Climate change contributes to challenges in maintaining a healthy and conducive learning environment within the classroom that affects students' wellness	3.56	Strongly Agree	6
10	The effects of climate change have noticeable consequences on the overall health and well-being of students attending our school.	3.59	Strongly Agree	2
Overall Weighted Mean		3.56	Strongly Agree	

On average, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the impact of climate change in student’s learning in terms of students’ health, manifested on the computed overall weighted mean of 3.56. The findings imply that heat makes it harder for students to learn. Students perform worse on tests when they’re hot. Rapid rises in heat gain due to exposure to hotter than average conditions compromises the body's ability to regulate temperature and can result in a cascade of illnesses, including heat cramps, heat exhaustion, heatstroke, and hyperthermia. Reduced blood volume and blood pressure also cause the heart to work harder, which can lead to heart failure, and severe dehydration can lead to acute kidney damage. Even healthy adults exposed to extreme heat can experience heat cramps, heat exhaustion or heat stroke. One possible reason for the effects observed is that pupils cannot concentrate or are distracted when temperatures in classrooms are too high and that this has negative consequences for an effective learning process. The trend toward more frequent, longer-lasting and more intense heat waves is a hallmark of the climate emergency that has resulted from humans burning fossil fuels and releasing planet-warming greenhouse gases.

Nigatu, Asamoah & Kloos (2014) mentioned that climate change affects human health in various ways. Health planners and policy makers are increasingly addressing potential health impacts of climate change. Assessing students’ knowledge, understanding and perception about the health impact of climate change may promote educational endeavors to increase awareness of health impacts linked to climate change and to facilitate interventions.

Children are at a higher risk due to their potentially greater exposures to climate-induced health risks, greater sensitivity, their dependence on caregivers, Ebi and Paulson (2007) physical, physiologic, and cognitive immaturity Bunyavanich, Landrigan , McMichael and Epstein (2003); Etzel, Crain, Gitterman, Oberg, Scheidt, Landrigan, (2003).

2.7. Physical Infrastructure

Table 16 presents the perceived impact of climate change in student’s learning in terms of physical infrastructure.

The teacher-respondents strongly agreed that investing in climate-resilient infrastructure is essential for ensuring the continuity and quality of education to ensure learning in the face of climate change, manifested on the highest computed recorded weighted mean of 3.58 (rank 1); while they strongly agreed that the disruptions to physical infrastructure caused by climate change, such as damage to school buildings or roads, impact student health and safety within the educational environment, had the lowest weighted mean of 3.49 (rank 10).

Table 16. Perceived Impact of Climate Change in Student’s Learning in terms of Physical Infrastructure

	<i>Physical Infrastructure</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	Increased heat posed by climate change necessitates modifications to the physical infrastructure of the school to enhance learning conditions	3.54	Strongly Agree	5
2	The increased heat influence the effectiveness of existing ventilation systems and cooling measures in classrooms and common areas.	3.53	Strongly Agree	7
3	Changing climate, including extreme temperatures, impact the durability and functionality of school buildings and facilities.	3.56	Strongly Agree	2.5
4	The challenges posed by climate change induced factors like warmer temperatures and changing weather patterns impact the physical infrastructure of schools and other educational facilities affecting the overall quality and maintenance of school buildings and facilities.	3.54	Strongly Agree	5
5	The disruptions to physical infrastructure caused by climate change, such as damage to school buildings or roads, impact student health and safety within the educational environment	3.49	Strongly Agree	10
6	The changes in temperature and rainfall patterns due to climate change impact the resilience of school infrastructure to withstand extreme weather events	3.50	Strongly Agree	9

7	The severe and frequent storms, flooding, and landslides, attributed to climate change, impact the structural integrity and safety of school buildings and facilities	3.51	Strongly Agree	8
8	Climate change-related factors influence the need for innovative and sustainable solutions to enhance the physical infrastructure of the school.	3.56	Strongly Agree	2.5
9	The vulnerability of school infrastructure to climate change-related hazards impact the overall learning environment for students	3.54	Strongly Agree	5
10	Investing in climate-resilient infrastructure is essential for ensuring the continuity and quality of education to ensure learning in the face of climate change.	3.58	Strongly Agree	1
Overall Weighted Mean		3.54	Strongly Agree	

On average, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the impact of climate change in student’s learning in terms of physical infrastructure, manifested on the computed overall weighted mean of 3.54. The findings underscore that climate-resilient infrastructure is that it is planned, designed, built and operated in a way that anticipates, prepares for, and adapts to changing climate conditions. It can also withstand, respond to, and recover rapidly from disruptions caused by these climate conditions. Climate resilience is the ability to anticipate, prepare for, and respond to hazardous events, trends, or disturbances related to climate. Improving climate resilience involves assessing how climate change will create new, or alter current, climate-related risks, and taking steps to better cope with these risks. Much of existing school infrastructure has not been designed to withstand the increasing impacts of climate change, such as severe storms, floods, and wildfires.

Means III, Laugier, Daw & Owen (2020) mentioned that climate change is challenging the way utilities plan and design their infrastructure. The variability of climate change repercussions adds new uncertainties to the fundamental assumptions of infrastructure engineering. Utilities are faced with the prospect of modifying existing planning and design practices to address the risks presented by climate change; however, the difficulty lies in determining for which climate risks utilities need to plan. This article evaluates the potential effects of climate change on water utility planning and design through survey and case studies. On the basis of these findings, various strategies for adapting to the wide range of projected climate change impacts are discussed. A general framework for evaluating the effects of climate change on facility planning and design is also presented. This framework helps utilities identify which aspects may be sensitive to climate change as well as options that can be used to reduce the risks associated with climate change uncertainty.

The study of Sucipto and Safitri (2029) analyzed the importance of green environmentally friendly school infrastructure development in supporting the learning process in schools. The results of their study indicated that green school infrastructure must have clean water, rubbish (the provision of separate bins, composters), feces, wastewater/drainage, green open space, noise/vibration/radiation.

The study of Mokaya (2013) found that improved academic achievement is associated with more adequate and well-spaced classrooms, adequate and ample spacing in the libraries, adequate science laboratories, adequate water and sanitation facilities and adequate participation in co-curricular activities.

2.8. Summary: Perceived Impact of Climate Change in Student’s Learning

The summary on the perceived impact of climate change in student’s learning is presented in Table 17.

Table 17. Summary on the Perceived Impact of Climate Change in Student’s Learning

	<i>Dimensions</i>	<i>Overall Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	Classroom Management	3.56	Strongly Agree	1.5
2	Classroom Activities	3.49	Strongly Agree	5.5
3	Students’ Concentration	3.50	Strongly Agree	4
4	Students’ Attendance	3.49	Strongly Agree	5.5
5	Students’ Participation in Class Discussion	3.44	Strongly Agree	7
6	Students’ Health	3.56	Strongly Agree	1.5
7	Physical Infrastructure	3.54	Strongly Agree	3
Grand Mean		3.51	Strongly Agree	

It can be noted that the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the impact of climate change in student’s learning in terms of classroom management; and students’ health, with the highest computed mean of 3.56 (tied at rank 1.5). This is followed by the impact of climate change in student’s learning in terms of physical infrastructure, with computed mean of 3.54 (rank 3); students’ concentration, with computed mean of 3.50 (rank 4); classroom activities; and student’s attendance, with computed mean of 3.49 (tied at rank 5.5); and students’ participation in class discussion, had the lowest computed mean of 3.44 (rank 7).

On average, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the impact of climate change in student’s learning, manifested on the computed grand mean of 3.51.

It is interesting to note that climate change impacted classroom management and student’s health in the school system. The awareness and perception of climate change can be influenced by teachers’ beliefs and classroom management practices. Students may experience the direct impacts of climate change, such as droughts, floods, declining water quality, and the spread of vector-borne illnesses. Taking into account the adverse impacts of climate change on human health, the importance of increasing knowledge and gaining essential skills is necessary to mitigate and adapt to its impacts and protect human health. The findings from the study will be useful to school

curricula developers looking to expand climate change education. This study also highlighted potential research gaps in education on climate change-related health in schools.

These changes in the climate, forced schools to adjust their activities accordingly. These is worsen by the rapid development of schools which has an impact to the local climate. The local climate change could affect the micro- environment such as plants, people and buildings, including external and internal school environment that causes discomfort during the process of teaching and learning in the classroom especially teachers and students. Result shows that the majority of the respondents felt uncomfortable with the changes of climate in student's learning, which need to be addressed (Puteh, Adnan, Ibrahim, Noh, & Che'Ahmad, 2014).

3. Level of Academic Performance of Students

Table 18 shows the frequency and percentage distribution on the level of academic performance of students.

Table 18. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution on the Level of Academic Performance of Students*

<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Grading Scale</i>	<i>Frequency (f)</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Outstanding	90-100	26	22.60
Very Satisfactory	85 – 89.9	67	58.30
Satisfactory	80 – 84.9	22	19.10
Fairly Satisfactory	75 - 79.9	0	0.00
Did Not Meet Expectation	Below 75	0	0.00
Total		115	100.00
Mean = 87.45 (Passed)			

Majority of the teachers reported that their students in their class performed rating range of 85-89.4, with the highest frequency of sixty-seven (67) response or 58.30% described as very satisfactory; twenty-six (26) or 22.60% reported that their students in their class performed rating range of 90-100 interpreted as outstanding; twenty-two (22) or 19.10% reported that their students in their class performed rating range of 80-84.4 interpreted as satisfactory.

Overall, the teachers reported that their students garnered passing mark academic performance as manifested on the computed mean of 87.45. This imply on a passing level of measurement of pupils achievement across various academic subjects. Teachers and education officials typically measure achievement using classroom performance, graduation rates, and results from standardized tests. The academic performance is measured by the final grade earned by the students in the class. Intellectual ability and skills of students reached in the academic context.

Academic success has a great influence on a student's self-esteem, motivation, environmental and climate factor, and perseverance in higher education. Poor academic performance or high failure rates may result in unacceptable levels of attrition, reduced graduate throughput and increased cost of education. This also reduces admission opportunities for tertiary students seeking higher degrees. Hence, students' academic performance has always been a topic of interest for educators. Educators and researchers have long been interested in identifying and understanding the variables that contribute to academic excellence. Many researchers have identified demographic, socio-economic, family and school factors as variables contributing to students' academic performance. Academic performance is frequently defined in terms of examination performance. In this study academic performance was characterized by the overall performance in each year which culminates in a Grade Point Average (GPA). The GPA score would take into account students' performance in tests, course work and examinations (Jayanthi, Balakrishnan, Ching, Latiff & Nasirudeen, 2014).

4. Test of Difference on the Perception of Teachers on the Impact of Climate Change on their Teaching when Grouped According to Dimensions

Table 20 presents the analysis of variance to test difference on the perception of teachers on the impact of climate change on their teaching when grouped according to dimensions.

Table 19. *Analysis of Variance to Test Difference on the Perception of Teachers on the Impact of Climate Change on their Teaching when Grouped According to Dimensions*

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
Classroom Management	115	417.1	3.626957	0.17953
Classroom Activities	115	410.8	3.572174	0.190272
Students' Concentration	115	408.6	3.553043	0.206197
Students' Attendance	115	400.6	3.483478	0.217883
Students' Participation in Class Discussion	115	398.8	3.467826	0.251675
Students' Health	115	400.6	3.483478	0.201918
Physical Infrastructure	115	396.6	3.448696	0.241468

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	2.958385	6	0.493064	2.318056	0.031677	2.109924
Within Groups	169.7393	798	0.212706			
Total	172.6977	804				

Decision: Ho is Rejected (Significant)

The computed F value of 2.318056 is greater than (>) the F-critical Value of 2.109924, using 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, therefore the Null Hypothesis is rejected, hence there was significant difference on the impact of climate change in teaching.

The findings of the study signify that the impact of climate change in teaching differs in terms of classroom management, classroom activities, students' concentration, students' attendance, students' participation in class discussion, students' health, and physical infrastructure. There are varying factors that affect the impact of climate change to educational system. These factors should be addressed differently to combat climate change and for the effective delivery of teaching-learning process.

Similarly, the study of Bardsley & Bardsley (2017) concluded discussing varying societal responses to reduce the different impacts of future climate change in teaching.

5. Test of Difference on the Perception of Teachers on the Impact of Climate Change to Student's Learning when Grouped According to Dimensions

The analysis of variance to test difference on the perception of teachers on the impact of climate change to student's learning when grouped according to dimensions is shown in Table 19.

Table 20. Analysis of Variance to Test Difference on the Perception of Teachers on the Impact of Climate Change to Student's Learning when Grouped According to Dimensions

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
Classroom Management	115	409.2	3.558261	0.185962
Classroom Activities	115	401.8	3.493913	0.222857
Students' Concentration	115	402	3.495652	0.197963
Students' Attendance	115	401.2	3.488696	0.215047
Students' Participation in Class Discussion	115	396.1	3.444348	0.211262
Students' Health	115	408.9	3.555652	0.21056
Physical Infrastructure	115	406.4	3.533913	0.196998

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	1.174584	6	0.195764	0.951202	0.457488	2.109924
Within Groups	164.2339	798	0.205807			
Total	165.4085	804				

Decision: Do Not Reject Ho (Not Significant)

The computed F value of 0.951202 is less than (<) the F-critical Value of 2.109924, using 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, therefore the Null Hypothesis is accepted, hence there was no significant difference on the impact of climate change to student's learning based from various dimensions.

The result signifies that there is no statistically detected difference on the impact of climate change to student's learning in terms of classroom management, classroom activities, students' concentration, students' attendance, students' participation in class discussion, students' health, and physical infrastructure.

Figure 3 illustrates the post hoc using scheffe test and means plot in determining where the difference lies on the perception of teachers on the impact of climate change on their teaching when grouped according to dimensions.

Figure 3. Post hoc using Scheffe Test and Means Plot in determining where the Difference lies on the Perception of Teachers on the Impact of Climate Change on their Teaching when Grouped According to Dimensions

The figure clearly illustrates the means plot that the difference on the impact of climate change in teaching lies between classroom management and physical infrastructure, as manifested on the highest and lowest mean values of the dimensions of the impact of climate change in teaching.

Teachers often face challenges in classroom management due to climate change-related factors such as extreme heat, flooding, or severe weather events. These factors can disrupt classroom activities, student engagement, and attendance, making it difficult for teachers to maintain an effective learning environment. Furthermore, physical infrastructure, including school buildings and facilities, can be negatively impacted by climate change. For example, rising temperatures and extreme weather events can lead to structural damage, such as roof leaks or heating, ventilation and airconditioning system failures. This can create unsafe or uncomfortable learning environments for both teachers and students.

6. Test of Relationship between the Impact of Climate Change to Teaching and Learning

The Pearson product moment coefficient of correlation to test relationship between the impact of climate change to teaching and learning is presented in Table 21.

Table 21. Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation to test Relationship between the Impact of Climate Change to Teaching and Learning

Sources of Correlations		Teaching	Learning	Decision/ Interpretation
Teaching	Pearson Correlation	1	0.902**	Very High Positive Correlation (Ho is Rejected)
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000	
	N	115	115	
Learning	Pearson Correlation	0.902**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000		
	N	115	115	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The computed Pearson r value of 0.902 denotes very high positive correlation. The computed P -value 0.000 is less than ($<$) 0.01 Alpha level of significance, therefore the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there was significant relationship between the impact of climate change to teaching and in learning.

The findings imply that as the impact of climate change to teaching becomes higher, there is a very high tendency that its impact to student's learning will also gets higher. High impact of climate change to teaching is linked to its high impact in learning in the school system. Climate change has a direct impact on education. The primary impacts of climate change on education arise from the effects of extreme weather events, such as heavy rains accompanied by flash floods, strong winds and hail storms with short and long-term consequences. Drought and increasing temperatures lead to poor harvests and food scarcity which have negative impacts upon educational attainment. Extreme weather events reduce the availability of safe drinking water, compromise sanitation and increase the incidence of weather related diseases such as malaria and diarrhea diseases, leading to absenteeism and possible withdrawal of children from school. Beside the primary impacts, climate change also has secondary impacts on education, arising from the ways in which households respond to, or choose to cope with and adapt to climate change as evidenced by income supplementing activities of household members, migration and child marriages.

Bangay (2020) claimed that the increasing attention to climate change and the current global economic crisis has underscored the need for approaches to education that equip and empower people of all ages to deal with uncertain environmental, economic and political futures. A range of educational and research initiatives already exist which could support this aim, however, policy and discussion continue to focus on technical solutions or 'knowledge transfer' without seriously engaging with the content of education.

7. Test of Relationship between the Impact of Climate Change to Teaching and Academic Performance of Students

Table 22 shows the Pearson product moment coefficient of correlation to test relationship between the impact of climate change to teaching and academic performance of students.

Table 22. Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation to test Relationship between the Impact of Climate Change to Teaching and Academic Performance of Students

Sources of Correlations		Teaching	Learning	Decision/ Interpretation
Teaching	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.190*	Very Low Negative Correlation (Ho is Rejected)
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.042	
	N	115	115	
Learning	Pearson Correlation	-0.190*	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.042		
	N	115	115	

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The computed Pearson r value of -0.190 denotes very low negative correlation. The computed P-value 0.042 is less than (<) 0.05 Alpha level of significance, therefore the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there was significant relationship between the impact of climate change to teaching and academic performance of students.

The findings signify that the higher the impact of climate change to teaching, there is a very low tendency that the academic performance of students becomes lower. Environmental destruction can dramatically affect the learning outcomes of students. Factors of climate change has an impact to student’s learning and performance in schooling.

Maxwell, Reynolds, Lee, Subasic & Bromhead (2017) elaborated that effective teaching and learning is the result of environmental factors. However, the precise organizational factors and psychological mechanisms behind these processes are still under investigation. Identifying the means to improve students' learning outcomes remains the subject of continuous academic inquiry and a key objective of government and international bodies. As a result of this interest, an immense body of work centered on the construct of climate change has emerged. Among other factors, empirical evidence has confirmed that climate change is powerful in affecting students' academic achievement.

8. Proposed Action Plan based from the Findings of the Study

Ensuring the continuity of quality teaching and learning amidst the escalating impacts of climate change is crucial for the Division of Zambales. This action plan aims to fortify schools against climate vulnerabilities through comprehensive strategies and proactive measures. By enhancing awareness, integrating policies, scaling up best practices, implementing monitoring systems, integrating climate change into curricula, and establishing risk mitigation mechanisms, the Division endeavors to create a resilient educational environment capable of withstanding and adapting to climate challenges. This plan not only safeguards educational continuity but also fosters sustainable practices that benefit the entire community.

The purpose of the proposed activities is to enhance schools' resilience to the impacts of climate change, build knowledge and awareness, and implement strategies that support mitigation and adaptation efforts. These initiatives will engage a range of stakeholders, including school administrators, teachers, students, parents, and community members, to create a comprehensive approach to climate change education and action.

Objectives

The general objective of the proposed activities is to improve the knowledge and awareness of the teachers and students on the impact of climate change and to provide mitigating techniques on how to address the problems.

The action plan focuses on addressing the increasing impacts of climate change on schools, ensuring uninterrupted access to quality education. By enhancing knowledge on climate vulnerabilities, integrating climate change into policies and plans, scaling up best practices, monitoring implementation, integrating climate change into curricula, and implementing risk mitigation mechanisms, the Division aims to build resilience within its educational system.

Proposed action plan is illustrated in Figure 4.

Ensured quality teaching and learning access amidst increasing impact of climate change in schools in the Division of Zambales

<i>Key Result Area</i>	<i>Proposed Activities</i>	<i>Persons Involved</i>	<i>Time Frame</i>	<i>Budget Requirement/ Source of Fund</i>	<i>Expected Outcomes</i>
1. Enhance specific knowledge on vulnerability of schools to the impacts of climate change.	Attendance to Climate Vulnerability Workshop This includes identifying climate risks (e.g., flooding, heatwaves, storms) and evaluating the school's infrastructure, operations, and student health and	School Principal, Teachers, Parents and Other Stakeholder Climate change specialists or consultants as Resource Speaker	2 days (16 hours)	School Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) P15, 000	Enhanced knowledge on the vulnerability of schools to the impacts of climate change

2. Integrate and harmonize climate change among schools policies and plans including Developmental Plan	Climate Change Policy: Integrating climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies into their policies and plans. Provide examples of best practices and successful case studies.	School heads and Teachers Resource Speaker: Policy advisors with expertise in education and climate change	2 days (16 hours)	School Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) P20, 000	A set of standardized policy recommendations for all schools to follow.
3. Scale up implementation of best practices among schools in mitigating the impact of climate change in teaching and learning	Attendance to the Best Practices Exchange Forum	Schools DRRM Coordinator District or Division DRRM Coordinator as Resource Speaker	1 day (8 hours)	Schools Division MOOE P20, 000	Schools gain new insights and actionable plans to improve climate change mitigation in teaching and learning.
4. Monitor and evaluate implementation of mitigating	Climate Action Monitoring Dashboard Develop a digital dashboard that schools can use to track their progress on climate change mitigation plans.	School Head and Teachers DRRM Coordinator as Resource Speaker	3 Days (24 Hours)	School Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) P20, 000	Schools can use data from the dashboard to make informed decisions and adjustments to their plans.
5. Integrate climate change in the curricula of students and training programs for teachers	Attendance to Climate Change Curriculum Development	School Heads and Policy Makers Schools Division Finance Staff, School Heads and finance staff	3 Days (24 Hours)	Schools Division MOOE P30, 000	Enhanced climate change resilience of DepEd
6. Implement risk transfer and social protection mechanisms on mitigating the impact of climate change on the educational system	Climate Resilience Fund and Insurance Options	Schools Division Financial advisors or experts in risk management and insurance	1 day (8 hours)	Schools Division MOOE P30, 000	Schools are better equipped to withstand and recover from climate-related challenges, minimizing disruption to the educational system.

Figure 3. Proposed Action Plan in Addressing the Impact of Climate Change to Teaching and Learning

Conclusion

Based on the foregoing results of the study, the researcher concluded that: (1) The teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the impact of climate change in teaching as to classroom management, classroom activities, students’

concentration. students' attendance, students' participation in class discussion. students' health and physical infrastructure (2) The teacher-respondents strongly agreed on the impact of climate change in student's learning as to classroom management, classroom activities, students' concentration. students' attendance, students' participation in class discussion. students' health and physical infrastructure (3) The teachers reported that their students garnered passing mark academic performance. (4) There was no significant difference on the impact of climate change to student's learning based from various dimensions. (5) There was a significant difference on the impact of climate change in teaching as to dimensions.(6) There was a very high positive correlation between the impact of climate change to teaching and in learning. (7)There was a very low negative correlation between the impact of climate change to teaching and academic performance of students. (8) The proposed action plan aimed in addressing the impact of climate change to teaching and learning in Zone 2, Schools Division of Zambales.

In view of the conclusion of the study, the following are recommended. (1) Campaign for climate change impact mitigation may be facilitated by schools to different stakeholders discussing on how to handle the effects of climate change in classroom management, classroom activities, student's concentration, student's attendance, student's participation in class discussion, student's health and physical infrastructure of the school. (2) Curriculum planners and stakeholders in the education sector may consider to adjust the curriculum with better funding to address the menace of climate change. (3) School heads may consider conducting a systematic evaluation of classroom learning environments, particularly for thermal comfort, to guide improvements in schools. Information gathered from learners, parents, and other stakeholders can serve as a foundation for enhancing educational quality and the effectiveness of teaching and learning, even amid the challenges posed by climate change. (4) Schools can organize workshops for teachers and students to help them better understand and cope with the challenges of climate change. These workshops will prepare teachers for effective classroom delivery under changing environmental conditions. (5) One major way of disseminating information on the menace of climate change is in the classroom with the collaboration of the teachers and students' organization like the YES-O Club and Science Club. The need for teachers' and students' awareness is necessitated to prevent impact of climate change and educate them in combating its effect in learning. (6) Teachers are encouraged to enhance innovative approaches addressing the impact of climate change in teaching and learning. (7) The proposed action plan in addressing the impact of climate change to teaching and learning in Zone 2, Schools Division of Zambales may be reviewed and critiqued for adoption by schools depending on its applicability. (8) Further studies in describing perceptions on the impact of climate change in teaching and learning may be conducted involving other variables and other locations to further validate results obtained from this study.

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